

Strengthening Civil Society Engagement for Inclusive Local Governance: Lessons from Simraungadh Municipality, Bara, Nepal

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Abstract

Good governance at the local level requires participatory decision-making, inclusive planning, and responsive budgeting. However, in Simraungadh Municipality of Bara District, Madhesh Province, practices of local governance were found weak during the consultation. The engagement of civil society organizations (CSOs), including citizen participation in planning and budgeting processes, remained minimal. Frequent political clashes created an institutional standstill, limiting opportunities for meaningful involvement. The planning exercise often remained limited to paperwork, with budget allocations narrowly focused on infrastructure development while critical social issues such as gender-based violence, child marriage, dowry practices, domestic violence, and drug abuse were neglected. Consequently, vulnerable groups, including women, children, senior citizens, persons with disabilities, marginalized groups, and pregnant and lactating women, were excluded from local policy priorities. This study employs a case study approach, drawing on participatory observations, consultation records, and project documentation from the Security and Justice Program, supported by the Foreign, Commonwealth & Development Office (FCDO) and implemented by Divya Development Resource Center (DDRC) in partnership with People in Need (PIN). Data were analyzed to assess how CSOs were engaged, capacitated, and mobilized to influence local government planning and budgeting. CSOs were strengthened through gender-transformative social norms (GT-SN) sessions and supported to develop action plans addressing local social issues. Structured consultations between CSOs and local government representatives enhanced dialogue on inclusive governance. In addition, small grants facilitated advocacy and community initiatives. As a result, CSOs emerged as active stakeholders in local governance, successfully lobbying for budget allocations to address social concerns. For the first time, Simraungadh Municipality allocated funds in line with CSO demands, thereby institutionalizing community voices in decision-making after the rigorous consultation and capacity enhancement with local governments and selected CSOs/CBOs under the seven-step planning process in fiscal year 2081/082. This case demonstrates that capacitated CSOs, when meaningfully engaged, can shift

local governments from infrastructure-centric priorities toward inclusive governance frameworks. The Simraungadh experience offers valuable lessons for advancing participatory and inclusive governance across Nepal.

Keywords: Civil Society Organizations (CSOs), local governance, participatory budgeting, inclusive development, civic engagement